

UnB PPGA

UnB PPGA Filter by publication year range:2021 to 2024

Scholarly Output

Entity: UnB PPGA · Within: All subject areas (ASJC) · Year range: 2021 to 2024 · Data source: Scopus, up to 16 Apr 2025

280

number of publications by authors
in UnB PPGA

▨ Incomplete year

Outputs in Top 10% Citation Percentiles (field-weighted)

Entity: UnB PPGA · Within: All subject areas (ASJC) · Year range: 2021 to 2024 · Data source: Scopus, up to 16 Apr 2025

Share of publications in UnB PPGA that are among the most cited publications worldwide field-weighted

20 (7.1%)

number of publications in the top 10% most cited publications worldwide

- % publications in top 10% most cited
- % publications in top 1% most cited
- ▨ Incomplete year

Publications in Top Journal Percentiles by CiteScore Percentile

Entity: UnB PPGA · Within: All subject areas (ASJC) · Year range: 2021 to 2024 · Data source: Scopus, up to 16 Apr 2025

Share of publications in UnB PPGA that are in the top journals by CiteScore Percentile

51 (20.2%)

number of publications in the top 10% journals by CiteScore

- % publications in top 10% journals
- % publications in top 1% journals
- ▨ Incomplete year

Most cited publications

Entity: UnB PPGA · Within: All subject areas (ASJC) · Year range: 2021 to 2024 · Data source: Scopus, up to 16 Apr 2025

Publication	Citations	Field-Weighted Citation Impact
Artificial Intelligence Regulation: a framework for governance. de Almeida, P.G.R., dos Santos, C.D., Farias, J.S. (2021) <i>Ethics and Information Technology</i> , 23 (3), pp. 505-525.	106	8.47
Food Supply Chains and Short Food Supply Chains: Coexistence conceptual framework. Thomé, K.M., Cappellesso, G., Ramos, E.L.A. and 1 more (2021) <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 278.	92	1.84
How can governance support collaborative innovation in the public sector? A systematic review of the literature. Lopes, A.V., Farias, J.S. (2022) <i>International Review of Administrative Sciences</i> , 88 (1), pp. 114-130.	58	9.48
Psychometric Properties and Correlates of Precarious Manhood Beliefs in 62 Nations. Bosson, J.K., Jurek, P., Vandello, J.A. and 159 more (2021) <i>Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology</i> , 52 (3), pp. 231-258.	56	9.20

Most cited publications

Publication	Citations	Field-Weighted Citation Impact
Public Innovation and Living Labs in Action: A Comparative Analysis in post-New Public Management Contexts. Criado, J.I., Dias, T.F., Sano, H. and 3 more (2021) International Journal of Public Administration, 44 (6), pp. 451-464.	43	3.47

Citation Count

Entity: UnB PPGA · Within: All subject areas (ASJC) · Year range: 2021 to 2024 · Data source: Scopus, up to 16 Apr 2025

1,570

number of citations received by publications in UnB PPGA

▨ Incomplete year

Citations per Publication

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▨ Incomplete year

5.6

average number of citations per publication in UnB PPGA

Field-Weighted Citation Impact

Entity: UnB PPGA · Within: All subject areas (ASJC) · Year range: 2021 to 2024 · Data source: Scopus, up to 16 Apr 2025

Views Count

Entity: UnB PPGA · Within: All subject areas (ASJC) · Year range: 2021 to 2024 · Data source: Scopus, up to 16 Apr 2025

15,988

number of Scopus views received by publications in UnB PPGA

/// Incomplete year

Outputs in Top Views Percentiles (field-weighted)

Entity: UnB PPGA · Within: All subject areas (ASJC) · Year range: 2021 to 2024 · Data source: Scopus, up to 16 Apr 2025

Share of publications in UnB PPGA that are among the most viewed publications worldwide
field-weighted

89 (31.8%)

number of publications in the top 10% most viewed publications worldwide

■ % publications in top 10% most viewed

■ % publications in top 1% most viewed

/// Incomplete year

Views per Publication

Entity: UnB PPGA · Within: All subject areas (ASJC) · Year range: 2021 to 2024 · Data source: Scopus, up to 16 Apr 2025

57.1

average number of Scopus views
per publication in UnB PPGA

▨ Incomplete year

Field-Weighted Views Impact

Entity: UnB PPGA · Within: All subject areas (ASJC) · Year range: 2021 to 2024 · Data source: Scopus, up to 16 Apr 2025

2.08

Field-Weighted Views Impact of
UnB PPGA

▨ Incomplete year

Publications by Journal quartile

Entity: UnB PPGA · Within: All subject areas (ASJC) · Year range: 2021 to 2024 · Data source: Scopus, up to 16 Apr 2025

Share of publications per Journal quartile by CiteScore Percentile

Researchers

Entity: UnB PPGA · Within: All subject areas (ASJC) · Year range: 2021 to 2024 · Data source: Scopus, up to 16 Apr 2025

Name	Scholarly Output	Most recent publication	Citations	<i>h</i> -index
1. Guarnieri, Patrícia	36	2024	231	18
2. Torres, Cláudio Vaz Vaz	36	2024	346	20
3. Matsushita, Raul Yukihiro	21	2024	24	11
4. Kimura, Herbert	20	2024	90	22
5. Pérez-Nebra, Amalia Raquel	19	2024	63	6
6. Demo, Gisela	16	2024	50	8
7. Thomé, Karim Marini	14	2024	171	12
8. Abbad, Gardênia da Silva	13	2024	34	8
9. Porto, Rafael Barreiros	13	2024	31	8
10. Rosano-Peña, Carlos	10	2024	35	7

Publication share by Subject Area

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Geographical Collaboration - Overall

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International, national and institutional collaboration by in UnB PPGA in the selected year range.

Academic-Corporate Collaboration

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Scholarly Output in UnB PPGA with both academic and corporate author affiliations

Top collaborating Institutions

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Institution	Co-authored publications ↓	Citations received for co-authored publications	Co-authors	Field-Weighted Citation Impact
1 Universidade de Brasília	273	1,553	275	0.79
2 Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina	27	78	18	0.53
3 National and Kapodistrian University of Athens	15	253	4	3.68
4 University of Ghana	14	218	7	3.65
5 Czech Academy of Sciences	14	235	6	3.70
6 Tilburg University	14	253	7	3.94
7 West University of Timisoara	14	219	2	3.62
8 Universidade Federal de Pernambuco	14	90	13	0.56
9 University Institute of Lisbon	14	217	5	3.45
10 Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University	13	154	4	3.11